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CONNECTING SCIENCE WITH SOCIETY

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Third Progress report on dissemination activities

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1. Introduction

This Deliverable describes the Communication and Dissemination activities performed by the EU-PolarNet project during its third reporting period (March 2018 – August 2019).

Dissemination activities vary according to the target audience and the message/result to be communicated/disseminated.

Important audiences for EU-PolarNet's dissemination efforts are:

- Research communities - from institutions, universities and national polar operators.
- Parliamentary and policy - European Commission, the European Parliament; national governments within member states.
- Business and Industry sectors - such as shipping, oil, gas, fisheries and tourism
- European public - including young people.
- Local Arctic communities; indigenous communities.
- Polar organisations including IASC, SCAR, IASSA, Arctic Council, Antarctic Treaty Secretariat etc.
- NGOs
- International networks and agencies such as the Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP); the Forum of Arctic Research Operators (FARO), INTERACT.
- Media.

The following main Communication and Dissemination activities have been carried out by the Project during the period analysed:

1. Dissemination at conferences and events: General Assemblies, Symposium, Conferences, Workshops, Scientific Consultations, Scientific Retreats, Policy Briefing and Lectures.
2. Online dissemination/outreach through EU-PolarNet website, social media channels, newsletter etc.

2. Dissemination at conferences and events

The EU-PolarNet Consortium actively communicates and disseminates the project and its results, by participating/organizing/co-organizing 42 events in more than 30 countries (mainly European but also non-EU countries), held regularly almost every month in the reporting period March 2018 - August 2019.

Different size events have been organized, according to the targeting audiences (from a wide audience of scientists to a selected group of experts and from senior to early career scientists) and their level of participation/interaction required: General Assemblies, Symposium, Conferences, Workshops, Scientific Consultations, Scientific Retreats, Policy Briefing and Lectures.

The table below lists the dissemination activities at conferences and events from March 2018 to August 2019. Part of them are also reported in the EU-PolarNet project website following this [LINK](#).

Name of event	Date	Location	Activity
4 th EU-PolarNet General Assembly and EU-PolarNet Symposium at the Estonian Academy of Science	27-28/03/2018	Tallinn, Estonia	At the 4th EU-PolarNet GA, 45 project partners and guests discussed the progress of EU-PolarNet and developed strategies for designing the Integrated European Polar Research Programme. The results from this meeting are summarised in D1.14 Minutes of the fourth General Assembly. EU-PolarNet also organised a public symposium at the Estonian Academy of Science just after the GA. The topic of the symposium was “The EU polar research priorities and the role and possibilities of smaller countries to contribute”. It included a keynote presentation named “In Ice and Snow - Expeditions to the Changing Arctic Ocean” and four presentations providing examples for different European Polar Programmes followed by a panel moderated discussion. The symposium was successful and EU-PolarNet decided to organize another symposium with its next GA.
The EU’s Arctic Research and Arctic scientific cooperation	19/03/2018	Levi, Finland	EU-PolarNet project members participated to disseminate project results. This event focussed on the EU’s contribution to Arctic research and the preparations towards the Arctic Science Ministerial meeting.
Da Terra australis incognita ao Programa Polar Português	13/03/2018	Lisbon, Portugal	EU-PolarNet project members participated to disseminate project results. The event includes a commemorative session marking the structured start-up of national scientific activities in Antarctica and laid the roots for a national polar program - the 4 th Polar Year. Several experts presented the developments of national polar science in the last ten years. A Memorandum of Understanding was also signed between the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) and the Bulgarian Antarctic Institute (IAB).
EU-Arctic Cluster Meeting	17/04/2018	Brussels, Belgium	EU-PolarNet project members participated and organized the event.
Symposium at the University of Cyprus on Polar Research	April 2018	Nicosia, Cyprus	EU-PolarNet project members participated to disseminate project results.
5 Years APRI – Anniversary of the Austrian Polar Research Institute	10/04/2018	Vienna, Austria	EU-PolarNet project members participated to disseminate project results. The Symposium programme is available HERE .

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Sustainable Adaptation to Climate Change and Globalization in Disko Bugt, West Greenland – Identifying Opportunities and Threats	05/2018	Ilulissat, Greenland	EU-PolarNet project members participated in this workshop on Sustainable Adaptation to Climate Change and Globalization in West Greenland.
Polar2018 and EU-PolarNet side event: European key research priorities for both poles	15-26/06/2018	Davos, Switzerland	EU-PolarNet project members participated and organized several sessions within the conference. EU-PolarNet presented the five EU-PolarNet white papers in a dedicated session called “EU-PolarNet - European Key Research Priorities for Both Poles”.
Arctic Observing Summit (AOS) 2018	24-26/06/2018	Davos, Switzerland	EU-PolarNet project members participated in an Arctic multi-stakeholder event on data collection as speaker/panellist with a focus on the role of industry in Arctic and ocean observations. The final report is available HERE .
UArctic Congress 2018 and EU-PolarNet side event: Applying the Sustainable Development Goals to the Arctic - Contributions from EU-PolarNet	3-7/09/2018	Oulu, Finland	EU-PolarNet project members participated and organized sessions. The congress was an integral part of the Finland’s Arctic Council chairmanship program and it was open to the public. The event highlighted the themes and priorities of the Finnish chairmanship, including the goals of the United Nations’ 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and the Paris Agreement under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. EU-PolarNet organised two sessions: 1) The UN Sustainable Development Goals: A signpost for societal relevant polar research? 2) Connecting polar research, policy and stakeholders across scales - examples from Europe and beyond
The Spanish IX Symposium on Polar Studies 2018	5-7/09/2019	Madrid, Spain	EU-PolarNet project members participated and disseminated project results. The Symposium assembled the entire Spanish scientific community investigating the Polar Regions in order to present and analyse the progress and existing perspectives.
EU-PolarNet Second Policy Briefing: At the frontline of climate change: Key changes in the Polar Regions that call for European action	26/09/2018	Brussels, Belgium	EU-PolarNet project members participated and organized the event, which brought pressing polar issues to the European Parliament. During the two-hour long policy briefing, EU-PolarNet presented its five polar white papers and fostered discussions on how European polar research and climate policies can contribute to the protection and sustainable development of the polar regions. The aim was to increase policy makers’ awareness on the far-reaching effects of climate-induced changes in the polar regions

Name of event	Date	Location	Activity
			and to enhance the dialogue between polar stakeholders from various backgrounds. More information HERE .
1 st Arctic Stakeholder Conference and annual Arctic Indigenous People Dialogue	17/09/2019	Brussels, Belgium	EU-PolarNet project members participated as panellist. The conference focused on "Knowing, developing and connecting the Arctic". The opening session addressed regional stability and cooperation, as well as climate change as the major challenge for the region. The EU engagement in the Arctic was highlighted. Panel discussions focused on Leveraging Sustainable and Innovative Investment in the Arctic. The Arctic Indigenous Peoples Dialogue discussed on Indigenous Peoples' rights in the European Union and on Sustainable Development of the Region from an Indigenous Perspective.
Rede ESPAÇO: Public launch session	09/2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Dissemination activities of EU-PolarNet
VI Jornadas dos Professores de Geografia	09/2018	Lisbon, Portugal	Dissemination activities of EU-PolarNet
CAFF Biodiversity Conference and AMAP/EU-PolarNet Stakeholder Workshop on Research Needs on Arctic Biology and Terrestrial Ecosystems	12/10/2018	Rovaniemi, Finland	EU-PolarNet co-organized the workshop on Research Needs on Arctic Biology and Terrestrial Ecosystems. The central theme of this workshop was to identify research needs for a better understanding of Arctic biology and terrestrial ecosystems and the factors that influence their functioning, including the many human uses of this area, in the light of the various changes occurring in the Arctic associated with climate change. The programme is available HERE .
Arctic Circle Assembly 2018 and EU-PolarNet side events: Research for societal benefit: Where polar research can make a difference and "And action! Moving beyond benevolent rhetoric in stakeholder engagement"	18-21/10/2018	Reykjavik, Iceland	EU-PolarNet members organized two sessions: 1) Research for societal benefit: Where polar research can make a difference; 2) And action! Moving beyond benevolent rhetoric in stakeholder engagement.
2 nd Arctic Science Ministerial	25-26/10/2018	Berlin, Germany	EU-PolarNet members participated in the event. The aims of this 2 nd ministerial meeting was to promote the results of the deliverables agreed at the 1st Arctic Science

Name of event	Date	Location	Activity
			Ministerial, increase capacity to respond to major societal challenges in the Arctic, encourage further scientific cooperation among a large number of countries and representatives of indigenous peoples.
WISTA International Conference 2018	23-26/10/2018	Tromsø, Norway	EU-PolarNet members participated and disseminated project results. "Breaking the Ice - Developing dialogues for sustainable business in the Arctic" was the main theme for the conference. It discussed opportunities and challenges for the maritime industry in the Arctic region taking into consideration the changing ice conditions and opening of new sailing routes.
Polar Data and Architecture summit	28-30/11/2018	Geneva, Switzerland	EU-PolarNet members participated, fostering the collaboration within the polar data community. The primary purpose of the workshop was to solidify the architecture development team and to continue progress on components already under development, work undertaken by the polar data community. A summary report is available HERE .
Arctic Futures Symposium: a view to the future	28/11/2018	Brussels, Belgium	Participation in the meeting
Dutch Annual Polar Symposium	7/12/2018	The Hague, Netherlands	Presentation of the work carried out by the EU-PolarNet Project
ArcticNet 2018	10-14/12/2018	Ottawa, Canada	Dissemination activities of EU-PolarNet Project
Arctic Frontiers and EU-Arctic Cluster side event on "Improved safety and environmentally sound operations in the Arctic Ocean - how to move forward?"	23/01/2019	Tromsø, Norway	EU-PolarNet project members participated and gave presentation in major Arctic multi-stakeholder event; Developed contacts/expanded network with Arctic maritime industry leaders. ARICE/EU PolarNet information have been presented during input and discussion as a plenary panellist, with focus on role of industry in Arctic and ocean observations and role of WOC. The interactive session discussed progress in taking a multidimensional approach to shipping-related safe operations in the Arctic Ocean.
Portuguese Air Force Academy	01/2019	Sintra, Portugal	EU-PolarNet project members gave lecture/disseminate project results.
Polar Symposium "Polar research and Europe: new challenges and	25-26/03/2019	Lisbon, Portugal	A public symposium organised by the University of Lisbon and EU-PolarNet offered a great opportunity to learn more about the Spanish Polar Programme, the Portuguese

Name of event	Date	Location	Activity
opportunities" and 5 th EU-PolarNet General Assembly.			Polar Programme, the Alfred Wegener Institute, and EU on-going initiatives supporting polar, especially Arctic, research. EU-PolarNet project members organized the 5 th EU-PolarNet General Assembly and the Symposium. The main issue discussed during the assembly was the progress achieved and the strategy on how to develop effectively the Integrated European Polar Research Programme.
Arctic Science Summit Week	22-30/05/2019	Archangelsk, Russia	EU-PolarNet project members participated to the conference disseminating the project results. More information available HERE .
ESA Living Planet Symposium	13-17/05/2019	Milan, Italy	EU-PolarNet project members participated to the conference disseminating the project results. Information on the symposium HERE .
EU-Arctic Cluster Meeting	4/06/2019	Brussels, Belgium	Organization of the event
Antarctic Treaty Consultative Meeting (ATCM) and EU-PolarNet/EPB side event "Connecting European Polar Research with Antarctic Policymakers"	01/07/2019	Prague, Czech Republic	EU-PolarNet and the EPB organised a side event at the Antarctic Treaty Consultative Meeting (ATCM) to stimulate discussions with ATCM delegates to identify societal relevant research needs in the Antarctic as an important contribution for national and international programmes. This effort is expected to be useful as a roadmap for the international management of the Antarctic continent at policy and operational levels. The societal relevant research needs will be included in the European Integrated European Polar Research Programme, which EU-PolarNet is currently developing. More than 50 delegates from 30 different countries or international organizations attended the successful event.
XIII International Symposium on Antarctic Earth Science, 2019	22-26/07/2019	Incheon, Republic of Korea	EU-PolarNet project members participated in the conference disseminating the project results. More information available HERE .
COMNAP & Workshop Towards harmonisation of polar infrastructure access	29-31/07/2019	Plovdiv, Bulgaria	EU-PolarNet project members participated in the conference disseminating the project results. More information available HERE .

3. Online Dissemination/Outreach

Online dissemination and outreach activities have been carried out through the EU-PolarNet website, social media channels, newsletter etc.

3.1 EU-PolarNet website

In line with what has been reported in the previous reporting period report, the EU-PolarNet website (www.eu-polarnet.eu) represents one of the main online dissemination tool for raising awareness about the project, sharing information related to the work of the consortium or affiliated projects and cooperation partners, and promoting upcoming events. The targeted audience ranges from the general public, to national and international policy makers, representatives from the industry, NGOs, interest groups and the wider science community. To meet the interest and needs of the various audience segments, the website offers both a wide range of informational static content and regularly updated contents, such as announcements and news.

The website also contains an internal part, which consortium members can log into, in order to retrieve consortium internal information and documents.

Since its launch, the EU-PolarNet website has been visited 32,041 times with a large geographical coverage. The website visits are tracked with the analytical tool Matomo.

Since the last reporting period the EU-PolarNet website has been visited 10,641 times mostly with the same impact ratios along the geographical areas documented previously. During 2019 the EU-PolarNet website has been visited 4,438 times with a large geographical coverage (figure 1)

Figure 1. Website visitors worldwide from January to mid July 2019

Figure 2. Website visitors worldwide since last reported period (January 2018-mid July 2019)

3.2 EU-PolarNet Social media channels

The main objective of the social media channels is to be used as a tool referring people to the EU-PolarNet website for more detailed information about the project development and results.

Facebook

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1442027029433733/>

EU-PolarNet uses its Facebook public group to share news, events and calls with its ca. 770 members. Any member can post content, once it has been approved by the group moderators. The main audience are researchers of all disciplines with a focus on early career scientists.

Twitter

<https://twitter.com/EUPolarNet>

The EU-PolarNet Twitter channel (@EUPolarNet) serves as a platform to both share news, events and calls, but also to report live from conferences and workshops, giving people digitally access to discussions. Currently 1748 people follow @EUPolarNet.

LinkedIn

<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/6971671/>

The EU-PolarNet LinkedIn group is used to share surveys and job postings from collaborating institutions. It currently has close to 80 members.

YouTube

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCqEzHkh6Q-ucxOFtd7UWHDA>

EU-PolarNet's Youtube channel features interviews with EU-PolarNet consortium members, in order to give the project and its participants a face. Furthermore, event recordings and event trailers are available on the channel. Currently 43 people have subscribed and 19 videos are available, which have been viewed 3,993 times.

Website referral

Facebook and Twitter attract most of the visitors. However, search engines and direct entries channel are the most relevant options to refer people to our website (figure 3) since the last reporting period.

Figure 3. Referral to EU-PolarNet website according to channel types

Channel Types

— Visits

3.3 EU-PolarNet Newsletter

In the third reporting period (March 2018 – August 2019) three newsletters have been issued, in September 2018, December 2018, and July 2019 recorded [HERE](#).

The EU-PolarNet newsletter informs recipients about news from the consortium and affiliated projects, reflects on developments in European polar research, introduces individual European polar research communities and gives a glimpse of conferences and events coming up in near future. So far three issues have been sent out to around 570 recipients.

4. Press Release

EU-PolarNet members have not published any press releases on EU-PolarNet nor have been addressed by the media on EU-PolarNet outcomes in this reporting period.

5. Outreach materials

The BAS media team has created a range of outreach materials for the project's launch, which are still regularly used. These materials include an EU-PolarNet flyer, which has been distributed and set up during various conferences and workshops, a roll-up and a poster. Furthermore USB-Hubs were created, which carried the slogan "Connecting Science with Society", as giveaways at conferences and workshops.

6. Publications

During this reporting period, EU-PolarNet has not published either scientific or informational publications in specialised journals that falls in the realm of the project.

7. EU Polar Cluster

<https://www.eu-polarnet.eu/eu-polar-cluster/>

The EU Arctic Cluster is a network of Horizon 2020 and a Framework Programme 11 funded Arctic projects. Currently it comprises eleven projects: *APPLICATE*, *ARCSAR*, *ARICE*, *BLUE-ACTION*, *EU-©EU-PolarNet Consortium*

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PolarNet, ICE-ARC, iCUPE, INTAROS, INTERACT, KEPLER and NUNATARYUK. The cluster thus merges a broad spectrum of research and coordination activities - ranging from the most up-to-date findings on permafrost and sea ice, from enhancing observation to improving predictions, and from networking research stations to coordinating access to icebreakers. In addition, two projects focussing on Antarctic Research have joined, these are Beyond EPICA and SO-CHIC. Since the cluster addresses now both Polar Regions it has been renamed into EU Polar Cluster.

During the last EU Polar Cluster meeting in Brussels, projects participants had the opportunity to contribute to a video recorded for the European Commission introducing their projects. A video with all the interviews has recently been being published through EC channels and is available on [Youtube](#).

In terms of outreach, EU-PolarNet members together with the EPB and the EU Polar Cluster communication task group are working to set up a new dedicated EU Polar Cluster website. The most important domains have been secured for the EU Polar Cluster.

EU-PolarNet's objective is to bring the insights from our various areas of expertise together in order to provide one entry point to EU funded Polar research. Jointly we are aiming at providing policy-relevant information and supporting among others the EU in implementing its integrated policy for the Arctic.